

Benzotriazole : An efficient, inexpensive and phosphine-free ligand for the palladium-catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura reaction[†]

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Manuscript received 11 March 2011, accepted 18 March 2011

Abstract : Benzotriazole has been disclosed as an efficient and inexpensive ligand for the palladium-catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reaction of arylhalides with arylboronic acids. This preparative convenient system afforded the corresponding coupling products, biaryls and terphenyls in good to excellent yields.

Keywords : Benzotriazole, cross-coupling, Suzuki reaction, palladium.

1. Introduction

The Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reaction, involving the coupling of an arylboronic acid with an organohalide, has proven to be an extremely useful synthetic tool in organic synthesis¹⁻⁶. Versatility of this reaction ranging from the synthesis of novel materials to industrial manufacturing of pharmaceuticals^{7,8}. These reactions are important for the preparations of biologically active molecules⁹ and herbicides¹⁰ and also find important applications in the fields of molecular recognition¹¹, liquid crystals^{12,13}, organic semiconductors¹⁴, or metal ligands for catalysis¹⁵. During the last decade, numerous modifications to the standard protocol have emerged to improve the scope¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and efficiency¹⁹⁻²³. It has been recognized that the ligands employed in these process has significant impact on the outcome of the reactions. It is well known that in Suzuki cross-coupling reaction the activity and selectivity of catalyst depend on the steric and electronic properties of the ligand system. Phosphine ligands are generally used to complex and activate the palladium species, and excellent results have been reported for the palladium-catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reaction²⁴⁻³⁰. However, phosphine ligands are sensitive to air, which places significant, limits on their synthetic applications.

In continuation of our recently developed methods for the copper-catalyzed C-N and C-S coupling reactions

using benzotriazole³¹⁻³³ as a ligand and its application in the tandem synthesis of indolo- and pyrrolo[2,1-*a*]isoquinolines by the addition of N-heterocycles onto *ortho*-haloarylalkynes, followed by intramolecular arylation³⁴ (Scheme 1), here in we expand the application of this one of the most inexpensive and simple ligand in the palladium-catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reaction. This new system is highly active and general for these reactions and, more importantly, extends the reaction scope in the synthesis of terphenyls.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Optimization of reaction conditions

To identify the optimal reaction conditions for the reaction, a number of palladium catalysts, including Pd(OAc)₂, PdCl₂ and several different organic solvents and ligands were examined in the reaction of 4-methoxyiodobenzene **1a** with phenylboronic acid **2b**. Parameters that were varied include the catalyst, solvent, and base, the results of these experiments are summarized in Table 1.

We first allowed 4-methoxyiodobenzene **1a** (1.0 mmol) to react with 1.2 eq. of phenylboronic acid **2b**, 2 mol% of Pd(OAc)₂, and 2.0 eq. of K₂CO₃ in 2.0 mL of toluene/H₂O (9 : 1) at 80 °C for 12 h. The desired coupling product **3a** was obtained only in 27% yield (Table 1, entry 1).

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Scheme 1

Table 1. Optimization of reaction conditions^a

Entry	Pd Cat./mol (%)	L/mol (%)	Base (equiv.)	Solvent	T (h)	Yield (%) ^b
1	Pd(OAc) ₂ /2	-	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	Toluene/H ₂ O (v/v = 9 : 1)	12	27
2	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	Toluene/H ₂ O (v/v = 9 : 1)	3	69
3	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	DME/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	58
4	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	MeOH	3	52
5	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	EtOH	3	55
6	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	EtOH/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	60
7	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	95
8	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /1.5	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	70
9	Pd(OAc) ₂ /2.5	L/5	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	73
10	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	Na ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	76
11	Pd(OAc) ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 2 : 1)	3	72
12	PdCl ₂ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 1 : 1)	3	68
13	PdCl ₂ /5	L/10	Na ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	79
14	PdCl ₂ /5	L/10	Cs ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	72
15	Pd ₂ dba ₃ /5	L/10	K ₂ CO ₃ /2	DMF/H ₂ O (v/v = 4 : 1)	3	80

^aAll reactions were performed with **1a** (1.0 mmol) and **2a** (1.2 eq.), under standard conditions unless otherwise indicated. ^bIsolated yields.

However, addition of 10 mol% of benzotriazole ligand and 5 mol% Pd(OAc)₂ to the reaction afforded the desired product **3a** in a 69% yield (Table 1, entry 2). From entries 3–7, it is apparent that the solvent has a significant

influence on the reaction; DMF/H₂O was found to be quite successful for the transformation. Compound **3a** was obtained in 95% yield, when DMF/H₂O (4 : 1) was used as the solvent (Table 1, entry 7). When we used

DME/H₂O (4 : 1), MeOH, EtOH, EtOH/H₂O (4 : 1) as a solvent, the desired product **3a** was obtained in 58, 52, 55 and 78% yield respectively (Table 1, entries 3–6). Different bases, such as Cs₂CO₃, Na₂CO₃ and K₂CO₃, were tested in this reaction system, but K₂CO₃ proved to be most effective (Table 1, entries 7–15). Using 1.5 eq. of K₂CO₃ afforded the coupling product in 70% yield (Table 1, entry 8). Decreasing the catalyst loading from 5 to 2.5 mol% afforded the coupling product **3a** only in 70% yield (Table 1, entry 9). Water and solvent ratio also affected the yield of the product, since compound **3a** was obtained only in 72% yield when DMF/H₂O was used in 2 : 1 ratio (Table 1, entry 11). Other palladium catalysts PdCl₂, Pd₂dba₃ were found to be inferior (Table 1, entries 12–15).

2.2. Scope of the ligand

After optimized reaction conditions were obtained, the scope of the reaction was investigated and the results are summarized in Table 2. The reaction of **1a–h**, with **2a–g** afforded the coupling products **3a–q** in good to excellent yields using the standardized reaction condition (Table 2, entries 1–17). Sterically hindered aryl iodide **1b** afforded the corresponding coupling products **3c** and **3f** in 86 and 81% yields respectively (Table 2, entries 3 and 6). Aryl iodides with electron-donating group at *ortho* and *para*

position, gave the coupling products in good yields (Table 2, entries 1–4, 6, 9, 10, 13 and 16). Presence of electron-withdrawing keto, cyano and nitro group in the aryl iodide provided the coupling products in excellent yields in less than 2 h at 60 °C (Table 2, entries 7, 8, 11, 14, 15 and 17). Coupling of sterically hindered 2,4,6-trimethoxyphenylboronic acid **2c** with 4-iodotoluene **1g** afforded the coupling product **3i** in 83% yield (Table 2, entry 9). Styreneboronic acid **2e** afforded the coupling product **3k** with 3-nitrophenyliodide **1h** in 92% yield (Table 2, entry 11). Naphthylboronic acid **2f** on coupling with electron donating **1g** and electron-withdrawing **1e** and **1h** aryl iodides afforded the coupling products **3m–o** in 90, 95 and 96% yields respectively (Table 2, entries 13–15). Further the reaction was performed with 4-(4-fluorobenzoyloxy)phenylboronic acid **2g** with aryl iodide **1g** and **1h** and afforded the coupling products **3p** and **3q** in 95 and 93% yields (Table 2, entries 16 and 17).¹

Scope of the developed chemistry was further extended for the coupling of aryl bromides (**4**) with arylboronic acids. The reaction of aryl bromides **4a–h**, with arylboronic acids **2a–f** afforded the coupling product **3a–l** in good yield (Table 3, entries 1–12). Aryl bromides with electron-donating group at *ortho* and *para* position, afforded the coupling products **3a–d**, **3f** and **3i–j** in good yields

Table 2. Suzuki–Miyaura coupling of aryl iodides with aryl boronic acids^a

Entry	Aryl halide	Boronic acid	Product	Yield (%) ^b
1		3a 95		
2		3b 94		
3		3c 86		
4		3d 88		
5		3e 90		
6		3f 81		
7		3g 95 ^c		
8		3h 96 ^c		

Table-2 (contd.)

9		3i	83				
10		3j	93				
11		3k	92 ^c				
12		3l	85				
13		3m	90				
14		3n	95 ^c				
15		3o	96 ^c				
16		3p	95				
17		3q	93 ^c				

^aAll reactions were carried out using 1 mmol of the aryl iodide 1 and 1.2 eq. of boronic acids 2 in the presence of Pd(OAc)₂ (5.0 mol%), L (10 mol%), and K₂CO₃ (2.0 equiv.) in 2.0 mL of DMF/H₂O (4 : 1) at 80 °C for 2–3 h. ^bThe yields are based on the product isolated by column chromatography. ^cReaction was carried out at 60 °C.

Table 3. Suzuki-Miyaura coupling of aryl bromides with aryl boronic acids^a

Entry	Aryl halide	Boronic acid	Product	Yield (%) ^b
1		3a 95		
2		3b 94		
3		3c 86		
4		3d 88		

Table-3 (contd)

5		4d		2b		3e	90
6		4b		2b		3f	81
7		4e		2b		3g	95 ^c
8		4f		2b		3h	96 ^c
9		4g		2c		3i	83
10		4g		2d		3j	93
11		4h		2e		3k	92 ^c
12		4d		2f		3l	85

^aAll reactions were carried out using 1 mmol of the arylbromide **1** and 1.2 eq. of boronic acids **2** in the presence of Pd(OAc)₂ (5.0 mol%), L (10 mol%), and K₂CO₃ (2.0 eq.) in 2.0 mL of DMF/H₂O (4 : 1) at 80 °C for 3–4 h. ^bThe yields are based on the product isolated by column chromatography. ^cReaction was carried out at 60 °C.

(Table 3, entries 1–4, 6, 9 and 10). The scope of the reaction was extended with sterically hindered biphenylboronic acid. Biphenyl-2-ylboronic acid **5a** afforded the terphenyls **6a–b** in 82 and 86% yields (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Coupling of biphenylboronic acid with aryl iodides.

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have found benzotriazole as an inexpensive and experimentally simple ligand for the palladium-catalyzed Suzuki–Miyaura cross coupling reactions of aryl halides with arylboronic acids. The process has been successfully applied for the synthesis of terphenyls

in excellent yields. The protocol is phosphine-free, simple and avoids the use of expensive and/or air sensitive ligands. Further studies on the scope of this ligand are currently underway in our laboratory.

4. Experimental

4.1. General

All reagents used were AR grade. Melting points were determined using a Buchi B-540 melting point apparatus. ¹H (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) were recorded on a Bruker 300 NMR in CDCl₃ (with TMS for ¹H and chloroform-*d* for ¹³C as internal references) unless otherwise stated. HRMS and LC-MS were recorded on Kratos MS50TC double focusing magnetic sector mass spectrometer and on QSTAR XL MS/MS system. Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (100–200 mesh). The reactions were monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) using aluminium sheets with silica gel 60 F254 (Merck). All glassware was oven dried, evacuated and

purged with nitrogen prior to use. All reaction temperature refers to bath temperatures.

4.2. General procedure for the synthesis of coupling products

The appropriate quantity of $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ and ligand **L** was added to a 5.0 mL round bottom flask containing the aryl halide (0.5 mmol), arylboronic acid (1.2 eq.) and K_2CO_3 (2.0 eq.) in 2.0 mL of DMF : H_2O (4 : 1). The flask was sealed with a cap containing a PTFE septum. The mixture was then heated at 80 °C until the aryl halides was consumed, as determined by TLC. The reaction mixture was quenched with H_2O (10 mL) and extracted with ethyl acetate (2×10 mL). The organic layer was then washed with brine (2×10 mL) and dried over Na_2SO_4 . The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the crude residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (100–200) mesh size using hexanes or a mixture of hexane and ethyl acetate as eluent. Coupling products were isolated in the yields reported in Tables 2 and 3.

4.3. Mechanism of Suzuki reaction

A possible catalytic cycle for the palladium-catalyzed C–C bond formation based on the previously reported mechanism is shown in Scheme 3^{2,12}. Presumably, $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ with ligand generates the palladium complex **7**, which on oxidative addition with aryl halide, results in the formation of intermediate **8**. Palladium complex **9** is formed by metathetic exchange under basic condition.

Scheme 3. Proposed mechanism.

Complex **9** undergoes transmetalation with boronic acid, resulting in the formation of intermediate **10**, which on reductive elimination affords the coupling product **3**, **6** and regenerate palladium complex **7**.

4.4. General characterization

^1H and ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR data (spin multiplicity is given by s : singlet, q : quartet, st : septet, m : multiplet, dt : doublet of triplets and ddt : doublet of doublets of triplets) :

4.4.1. 3-Nitro-4'-vinylbiphenyl (**3k**) : Off white solid, 92%, m.p. 65–67 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 8.36 (1H, s), 8.11 (1H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 7.84 (1H, d, J 7.1 Hz), 7.54–7.37 (5H, m), 6.73 (1H, q, J 10.8 Hz), 5.78 (1H, d, J 17.7 Hz), 5.26 (1H, d, J 10.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 148.7, 142.3, 137.8, 136.3, 135.9, 132.7, 129.7, 127.2, 126.9, 126.6, 121.9, 121.6, 114.8; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2$: 225.08; found : 348.99689.

4.4.2. 1-(4-(Naphthalene-1-yl)phenyl)ethanone (**3n**) : White solid, 95%, m.p. 90–91 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 8.00 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.83–7.74 (3H, m), 7.51–7.46 (2H, m), 7.43–7.36 (2H, m), 7.33–7.31 (2H, m), 2.58 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 197.8, 145.7, 138.9, 135.9, 133.7, 131.1, 130.3, 128.3, 126.9, 126.3, 125.9, 125.3, 26.7; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$: 246.10; found : 246.18.

4.4.3. 1-(3-Nitrophenyl)naphthalene (**3o**) : White crystalline solid, 96%, m.p. 55 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 8.37 (1H, s), 8.30 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.94–7.91 (2H, m), 7.83 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 7.77 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.65 (1H, t, J 9.3 Hz), 7.57–7.49 (2H, m), 7.44 (2H, t, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 148.3, 142.4, 137.5, 136.1, 133.8, 131.1, 129.2, 128.8, 127.2, 126.7, 126.2, 125.3, 125.0, 124.8, 122.2; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2$: 249.08; found : 249.20.

4.4.4. 4'-(4-Fluorobenzyloxy)-4-methylbiphenyl (**3p**) : White crystalline solid, 95%, m.p. 100–105 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.44–7.31 (6H, m), 7.15 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.02–6.91 (4H, m), 4.96 (2H, s), 2.29 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 164.1, 160.9, 157.9, 137.8, 136.4, 134.1, 132.7, 129.4, 129.3, 129.2, 127.9, 126.6, 115.6, 115.3, 115.0, 69.4, 21.0; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{FO}$: 348.99637; found : 348.99689.

4.4.5. 4'-(4-Fluorobenzyloxy)-3-nitrophenyl (**3q**) : Yellow crystalline solid, 93%, m.p. 65–66 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 8.31–8.30 (1H, m), 8.07–8.03

(1H, m), 7.78 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.50–7.45 (3H, m), 7.37 (2H, q, *J* 5.7 Hz), 7.03–6.97 (4H, m), 4.99 (2H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 164.2, 160.9, 159.1, 148.7, 142.3, 132.5, 132.4, 131.5, 129.7, 129.4, 129.3, 128.3, 121.5, 121.4, 115.8, 115.5, 69.5; HRMS calcd. for C₁₉H₁₄NO₃F : 323.10; found : 323.19.

4.4.6. 2-(4-Methylphenyl)-biphenyl (6a) : Colorless oil, 82%; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.33–7.25 (4H, m), 7.23–7.18, (1H, m), 7.13–7.07 (6H, m), 6.95–6.89 (5H, m), 6.54 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.29 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 141.7, 140.5, 138.5, 137.1, 131.7, 130.6, 129.8, 129.7, 128.6, 127.8, 127.4, 127.2, 127.0, 126.4, 121.1; HRMS calcd. for C₁₉H₁₆ : 244.13; found : 244.09.

4.4.7. 2-(3-Nitrophenyl)-biphenyl (6b) : White solid, 86%, m.p. 60–62 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 8.00–7.96 (2H, m), 7.39 (4H, s), 7.32–7.22 (2H, m), 7.14 (3H, s), 7.04–7.03 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 148.1, 143.3, 141.0, 140.5, 138.0, 136.1, 130.8, 130.3, 129.9, 128.7, 128.6, 128.2, 127.9, 127.0, 124.6, 121.5; HRMS calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃NO₂ : 275.19; found : 275.09.

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge the University of Delhi for the financial support. RRJ and RC thanks DU and UGC for the fellowship.

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